

A Generic Lumped-Parameter Model for Stators with Tooth-Wound Winding

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Abstract -- This paper introduces a thermal modeling method for the prediction of the temperature in a stator with concentrated tooth-winding using a lumped-parameter thermal network (LPTN). By analogy with the electrical circuits, the thermal network of the machine has been developed. The network consists of thermal resistances, thermal capacitances, and current sources. The different principles of heat and heat flow in all directions are taken into account. The parameters of the model are calculated based on analytical relations and experiments. Sensitivity analysis and multi-objective optimization using genetic algorithm (GA) has been conducted for tuning the parameters of the model. The optimization is intended to achieve a trade-off solution which gives the best agreement between the calculated and measured temperatures in different parts of the machine. The model is implemented on the stator of a concentrated winding PMSM. For validating the model, experimental results are presented and compared with the simulated ones.

Index Terms—Lumped-Parameter thermal model, multi-objective optimization, permanent magnet synchronous machine, thermal analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

THE negative ecological footprint of the combustion engines, global warming and reducing CO₂ emission as well as fossil fuel shortage have a major impact on the research and development of electrical machines [1]. In recent decades, more and more electrical machines have been integrated into road vehicles according to the increasing demand for comfort and cost reduction. In the context of the automotive industry, the use of electric and electronic equipment is rapidly growing. Many efforts have been devoted by car manufacturers to electrify some vehicle functions e.g. traction, steering, braking etc. [2].

PMSMs are particularly used in automotive [3] and aerospace applications [4] due to their high torque, power density, and high energy efficiency. PMSMs in the automotive applications are often overloaded in very short consecutive time-intervals, due to high dynamics in operation. Therefore, higher current densities result in large copper losses and higher temperatures, which might shorten the machine's life as the windings' electrical insulation will be subject to higher thermal stresses [5]. Moreover, the thermal stress inside the PMSMs leads to the temperature rise in the permanent magnets, which may result in their irreversible demagnetization. Therefore, an appropriate cooling mechanism is necessary for these machines.

In order to meet the customer requirements, achieve the optimal design, and minimize the risk and fault occurrence inside the machine, the thermal analysis of the electrical machine in addition to the electromagnetic one needs to be addressed. An important source of loss in this type of machine is the copper loss in the stator coils, but some losses are also produced in the iron core of the machines and in the

permanent magnets [6]. The thermal analysis of electrical machines has received less attention than the electromagnetic one. As a matter of fact, an accurate thermal management in an electrical machine is a more difficult and complicated issue than the electromagnetic design. Problems related to the heat transfer can be avoided by utilizing empirical knowledge of the machine constants available in the literature [7].

The modern approaches in the thermal analysis of the electrical machines are LPTN method, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) for conduction, and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for convection. These approaches have advantages and disadvantages; one of the main differences is the computation time. Once the thermal models are developed, the computational cost of analytical LPTN is much lower compared to the numerical methods [8]. However, the accuracy of any thermal model for electrical machines relies upon fine-tuning of its parameters, due to uncertainties in materials properties, manufacturing tolerances, assembly process, and interaction with other electrical drive components [9]. Developing of an LPTN model is a difficult task because of the complex machine geometry and different modes of heat transfer.

Although LPTNs can provide good temperature estimation, their computational cost can still be excessive for the online implementation and a trade-off between accuracy and computational speed is necessary [10].

In this paper, a thermal LPTN is developed for the calculation of the temperature distribution in the stator of a commercial concentrated-winding PMSM designed for a power-steering application. However, it can be extended for the thermal modeling of the stator of any kind of electrical machines with concentrated winding. Only copper losses occurring in the stator winding is considered. The LPTN for the complete machine is scaled to half of one stator tooth. The heat flow in all three directions, i.e. axial, radial, and circumferential ones, is considered. Moreover, different heat transfer mechanisms including convection, conduction, and radiation are modeled using four different types of thermal resistances. Two identical prototypes comprising only the stator and insulation material instead of the rotor and end-caps have been used for the calculation and the validation of the thermal parameters. Finally, an optimization algorithm based on multi-objective GA has been used for tuning the values of the thermal model parameters based on the comparison between the experimental and the calculated results.

II. LUMPED PARAMETER THERMAL NETWORK MODEL

A. Modeling symmetries

The heat flow around the perimeter of the machine in the radial direction is generally assumed to be symmetrical. If there are n_{as} identical heat flow paths, the symmetry can be

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used to scale thermal resistances of single stator tooth to equivalent thermal resistances. Symmetry factor n_{os} is equal to the number of teeth. Consequently, the equivalent thermal resistance for the thermal network representing the whole machine is only $1/n_{os}$ of the thermal resistance for one tooth.

Further, in the circumferential direction, the heat flows both clockwise and counterclockwise. Therefore, the thermal resistance between the thermal node on the tooth and the node in the slot has to be further divided by a factor 2 [11].

B. Calculation of Thermal Resistances

When creating a thermal network, there are four types of thermal resistances: conductive, convective, radiative and contact thermal resistances [14]. In general, these resistances are calculated by (1) [12]:

$$R_{th} = \frac{1}{kS} \quad (1)$$

where S (m^2) is the heat transfer area and k ($W/m^2\text{ }^\circ C$) can be the convection, conduction, radiation or contact coefficient.

C. Calculation of thermal capacitances

Thermal resistances are necessary for obtaining the steady-state temperature, while the thermal capacitances are used to simulate the transient behavior. Thermal capacity C_{th} ($^\circ C/J$) is dependent on the volume V (m^3), material density ρ (kg/m^3) and specific thermal capacitance C_{ths} ($J/kg\text{ }^\circ C$) [12]:

$$C_{th} = V \cdot \rho \cdot C_{ths} \quad (2)$$

D. Power loss Calculation

Copper losses are the main type of losses, which influence the temperature rise inside the different parts of electrical machine.

In this paper, the other types of losses are neglected.

E. Determination of Convection Coefficient

Heat is always transferred simultaneously by conduction and convection. Convection is defined as the heat transfer between a region of higher temperature and a region of a cooler temperature that takes place as a consequence of motion of the cooling fluid relative to the solid surface. There are two types of convective heat transfer: Forced and Natural Convection. In the forced convection, external instruments such as pumps or blowers assist the flow of the coolant. Natural convection is caused by density variations resulting from temperature differences [7].

The thermal resistance of convection can be calculated by (1) where h_{cv} ($W/m^2\text{ }^\circ C$) is the convective heat transfer coefficient. The value of this coefficient is strongly dependent on the viscosity of the coolant, the thermal conductivity, specific heat capacity and the flow velocity of the medium. For natural convection in the air around a horizontally mounted, unfinned cylindrical motor with diameter D (m), with ambient temperature close to the room temperature, an empirical equation depending on the temperature difference θ ($^\circ C$) between the motor cylinder and the surrounding, can be employed as [7]:

$$h_{cv} \approx 1.32 \left(\frac{\theta}{D}\right)^{0.25} \quad (3)$$

III. METHODOLOGY

The calculation process of the thermal resistances and the

thermal capacitances is performed in MATLAB-script. For the calculation of the thermal resistances and capacitances, parameters and dimensions of the machine need to be known. The flowchart of the developed procedure for the calculation of the thermal resistances and capacitances is shown in Fig. 1.

The machine dimensions and material properties are inputs. Subsequently, the calculation of thermal resistances and capacitances for different parts of one tooth is followed. The radiation and convection resistances are calculated for the whole machine and then scaled by the symmetry factor. After solving the thermal network, the temperatures are calculated. If there is a discrepancy between simulation and measurement, sensitivity analysis and optimization procedure of critical parameters can be performed for a more accurate determination of the unknown parameters.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the developed Matlab-script.

Fig. 2 represents the developed LPTN Simulink model which considers radial, axial and circumferential heat transfer for one half of one stator tooth. It means that it is a reduced version of complete thermal network due to symmetries for the sake of simplicity and lower computational effort.

Fig. 2. Scaled LPTN Simulink model of the stator.

According to [7], the thermal conductivity in the axial

direction is notably lower than the one in the radial direction. However, the experimental findings show a non-negligible heat transfer in the axial direction.

This LPTN consists of 6 thermal capacitances, 2 current sources and 23 thermal resistances, which capture all the key thermal parameters and temperature rising, as well as the main heat transfer paths. A preliminary value of these parameters has been determined based on the motor's geometry and the material's physical properties. Thermal nodes are the same as those associated with the thermocouples positions presented in the next section.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL FACILITIES

A. Test Bench and Motor Prototypes

Two identical thermal prototypes have been built in order to ensure the plausibility of the measurements. Both prototypes consist of a commercial stator of 12-slots/10-poles PMSM with concentrated winding for the automotive applications, having the main parameters reported in Table I.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE INVESTIGATED PMSM

Parameters of the Investigated PMSM		
Parameter	Unit	Value
Rated Power	W	650
Rated speed	rpm	1250
Voltage	V	12
Pole pairs	-	5
Stator outer diameter	mm	90
Stator axial length	mm	50

The rotor and the end-caps of both prototypes have been replaced by a plastic cylinder made of PolyEtherEtherKetone (PEEK) insulation material shown in Fig. 3. It ensures, that the heat flows from the winding to the ambient only through the stator yoke. PEEK is thermoplastic with excellent mechanical and chemical properties that are retained to high temperatures.

The 3-phase winding has been replaced by a single-phase one, which has been wound around the teeth. As it can be seen from Fig. 4, all the coils are connected in series and a single wire is used for the whole winding. In this way, the uniform temperature distribution around the perimeter of the machine is ensured and extra resistance and losses at the coil connections are avoided.

Fig. 3. PEEK.

Fig. 4. Winding connection.

Fig. 5. Placement of temperature sensors.

B. Placement of Thermal sensors

Each thermal sample is equipped with K type thermocouples (9 in total), installed by means of high thermal conductivity adhesive material. Eight thermocouples are placed on the tooth, see Fig. 5, and one (number 5, not shown here) is measuring the ambient temperature.

The thermocouples are attached to the winding, end-winding, tooth head, middle of tooth and two of them are embedded in the yoke and tooth. During the experiments all temperatures were recorded by an oscilloscope.

C. Data of the Prototypes

For the construction of two prototypes, the stator of a 12-slots / 10-poles PMSM used for the automotive application with concentrated winding has been used. Some of the machine's parameters are reported in Table I. and Table II.

TABLE II
MATERIALS OF THE INVESTIGATED PMSM

Machine Part	Material
Stator iron	M800-50A
Winding	Copper
Winding Insulation	Durethan

D. Experimental Test and Measurements description

The aim of the experimental work in the ambient with natural convection is to determine the value of radiation resistance R_r and to verify the accuracy of results based on the LPTN model.

Thermal test with DC supply is one of the simplest methods for determination of thermal resistances. This method has the advantage of limiting the losses in the machine to the copper DC losses, which can be easily calculated. The main drawback of this method is that it provides the convection and radiation resistance together and it is not easy to separate them (R_{1r} and R_{2r} in Fig. 2). For the more accurate calculation of the radiation resistance, the test should be done in a vacuum chamber [13]. During this test, the machine is supplied by a DC power supply. However, in our case, the vacuum chamber

was not available. The experiment was carried out until the temperatures reached the steady-state.

E. Determination of Radiation and Natural Convection Resistance

The radiation resistance depends on both geometrical and thermal characteristics of the motor and on the ambient temperature where the motor is operating. This resistance can be neglected when the motor is running at nominal speed and the forced convection provides the cooling of the motor. However, in this case, when the rotor has been replaced by a plastic part, radiation resistance plays an important role. The sum of radiation resistance and natural convection resistance can be calculated by:

$$R_{rc} = \frac{T_F - T_A}{P_T} = \frac{122.3^\circ\text{C} - 20^\circ\text{C}}{14.8\text{ W}} = 6.91^\circ\text{C/W} \quad (4)$$

where T_F ($^\circ\text{C}$), T_A ($^\circ\text{C}$) and P_T (W) is the motor frame temperature, ambient temperature, and copper loss obtained from thermal DC test.

F. Determination of contact coefficient between winding and stator core

The thermal behavior at the contact surface between two solids is a complex phenomenon. Usually, the heat transfer between two interconnected objects can be described by a contact resistance. The heat transfer across the gap between the joint surfaces depends on the finish of the surfaces. The thermal resistance of joint surfaces is the most significant inaccuracy factor in electrical machines. Determination of this resistance may prove difficult without measurements. However, since the contact thermal resistance play a non-negligible role in the heat transfer calculation, certain empirical values of contact thermal resistances have to be known [7].

The contact resistance depends on the surface roughness to a great extent and on the pressure which is holding two contact surfaces together. In the thermal network displayed in the Fig. 2, four contact resistances have been taken into account. Their values have been calculated by (1).

Fig. 6 shows the thermal resistances between the thermal sensors which have been placed on the winding in the slot and inside the drill in the radial and axial midpoint in the tooth. This part of the thermal network shown in Fig. 6 comprises of five thermal resistances, namely: R_{1cf} , conduction resistance of the tooth, R_{2cf} , contact resistance between the tooth and insulation, R_{3cf} , conduction resistance of the insulation, R_{4cf} , contact resistance between the insulation and the winding, R_{5cf} , conduction thermal resistance of the winding.

Based on the experimental measurements, the value of the total thermal resistances between sensor 3 and sensor 2 has been calculated according to (4) using respective temperatures as $R_{23} = 21.429^\circ\text{C/W}$.

Fig. 6. Thermal resistances between two thermal sensors.

The values of the conductive resistances have been calculated from the dimensions and material properties. Then the lumped contact resistance between sensors 2 and 3 is equal to the sum of R_{2cf} and R_{4cf} and can be expressed as follows:

$$R_{23cnt} = R_{23} - (R_{1cf} + R_{3cf} + R_{5cf}) = 15.04^\circ\text{C/W} \quad (5)$$

Finally, the value of contact coefficient $k_{cn} = 193.12\text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$. It should be noted, that it is a value of contact coefficient for the total resistance between winding and tooth iron which is composed of contact coefficient between winding and insulation and between insulation and iron.

V. COMPARISON OF SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS BEFORE OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

In Fig. 7 is shown a comparison between the simulated and measured temperature of the winding in the slot, end-winding and the tooth. The measurement has been performed with a constant value of 98 At (Ampere x tum), until the winding temperature reached a steady state. It can be seen that the temperature difference at steady state is approximately 25 K for the winding, which is caused by an inaccurate calculation of the thermal parameters and low resolution of the LPTN. The temperature difference during the transients is more significant, that's why a tuning of thermal parameters needs to be done.

Fig. 7. Comparison of simulated and measured temperatures of the winding (a), tooth (b) and end-winding (c) before optimization.

VI. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Sensitivity analysis determines the significance of design variables on certain outputs. A sensitivity analysis has been made to identify the most sensitive parameters of the model and to reduce the number of optimization variables used in the optimization. The LS-OPT software has been used for both

optimization and sensitivity analysis. The results of the sensitivity analysis based on the Monte Carlo study are shown in Fig. 8. This analysis provides among other things a Correlation Matrix, where the parameters with the strongest influence on the respective simulated temperature can be seen. Those parameters are provided in Table III.

Fig. 8. Correlation Matrix obtained from Monte Carlo Analysis.

The least significant ones can be removed from the optimization procedure resulting in the reduction of the computational effort.

At first, the sensitivity analysis has been performed manually by changing the convection coefficient $\pm 30\%$. However, this kind of sensitivity analysis takes a lot of effort. Therefore, Monte Carlo Analysis has been performed using the LS-OPT optimization software. This analysis provides a correlation matrix, from which the parameters with the strongest influence on the respective simulated temperature can be identified. Those parameters are reported in Table III.

TABLE III
SELECTED PARAMETERS FOR TUNING PROCEDURE

Name	Value		Error (%)
	Before Optimization	After Optimization	
Contact coefficient (W/m ²⁰ C)	193,23	211,3	9,35
Convection coefficient of the yoke (W/m ²⁰ C)	7,898	10,68	35,2
Specific thermal capacity of the Stator lamination (J/kg ⁰ C)	460	456,53	0,0076
Specific density of the stator lamination (kg/m ³)	7680	7948,3	3,49
Convection coefficient of the end-winding (W/m ²⁰ C)	12,96	15,99	23,37

VII. OPTIMIZATION OF THERMAL PARAMETERS

Parameter identification is a non-linear inverse problem which can be solved using mathematical optimization. There are several software for the parameter identification. In this case, LS-OPT has been used. System parameter identification (or calibration) is a commonly used feature in LS-OPT. The procedure consists of minimizing the mismatch between two curves. These two curves typically consist of a two-dimensional experimental target curve and a computed curve. The computed curve is a variable response which is dependent on the system parameters [14].

It is important to note that the tuned values of the selected parameters do not actually have a physical meaning as the only objective of the procedure is to minimize the temperature prediction error. Only their reference values were determined based on the physical properties of the used materials, the motor geometry, and on the base of preliminary manual tuning [15].

VIII. COMPARISON OF SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AFTER OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

Multi-objective optimization problems (MOOPs) are significantly different from the single-objective optimization ones. MOOPs do not have a single optimal solution, but there is a set of solutions that reflect the trade-offs among objectives which are often in conflict. From the mathematical point of view, MOOPs have therefore several solutions which are referred to as a Pareto Optimal Frontier (POF) [16]. A multi-objective GA method has been adopted for the optimization process.

The curve in Fig. 9 displays the optimal limit (Pareto Front) that has been achieved under constraints defined in LS-OPT. On this curve or close to it are located the “best” designs. One of these designs has been selected as the most optimal solution. The parameters values (after optimization) of the selected optimal solution are reported in Table III. These parameters have been used as input parameters for the LPTN-script. The comparison of simulation results with measurements is shown in Fig. 10. The simulated curves in this figure are calculated with the set of optimal parameters for which the temperature discrepancy for the winding is the lowest. It can be seen that there is still a temperature difference for other two test points. On the curve in Fig. 9 are not such designs for which the temperature difference is the lowest for the winding, tooth and end-winding at the same time. Therefore, we have selected the optimal solution from the Pareto Front for which the temperature discrepancy for the winding is the lowest.

Fig. 9. Tradeoff plot of the optimization results.

The optimization described above was conducted with a population size of 30 samples for 100 generations.

Fig. 10. Comparison of simulated and measured temperature in the winding (a), tooth (b) and end-winding (c)

IX. CONCLUSION

The focus of this paper was the thermal modeling of a PMSM stator using LPTN. The goal was to determine the temperature rising in different parts of the machine's stator due to copper losses. The developed LPTN was implemented in Matlab/Simulink. To verify the simulation results, temperature measurements were performed on two prototypes, to validate the employed analysis. Discrepancy between the measurements and simulation results has been found. In order to reduce this mismatch, the sensitivity analysis and optimization procedure of selected thermal

parameters were employed. There was a relatively good agreement between the calculated and experimental results

X. REFERENCES

- [1] T. Finken and K. Hameyer, "Design of Electric Motors for Hybrid-and Electric-Vehicle Applications," in ICEMS, 2009.
- [2] B. Lequesne, "Automotive Electrification: The Nonhybrid Story," in *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 40-53, June 2015, doi: 10.1109/TTE.2015.2426573.
- [3] A.C.Pop, J.J.C. Gyselinck, D. E. Pinto and I. Vintiloiu, "Optimization of low-power brushless pm-machines for automotive applications with focus on high-volume mass production." *IEEE transactions on industrial electronics* 64.12 (2017): 9767-9775.
- [4] Kefalas, Themistoklis D., and Antonios G. Kladas. "Thermal investigation of permanent-magnet synchronous motor for aerospace applications." *IEEE Transactions on industrial electronics* 61.8 (2013): 4404-4411.
- [5] C. Sciascera, M. Galea, P. Giangrande, and C. Gerada, "Lifetime consumption and degradation analysis of the winding insulation of electrical machines," in Proc. 8th IET Conf. Power Electron., Mach. Drives, 2016, pp. 1-5.
- [6] M. Popescu, D. Staton, D. Dorrell, F. Marignetti, and D. Hawkins, "Study of the thermal aspects in brushless permanent magnet machines performance," in 2013 IEEE Workshop on Electrical Machines Design, Control and Diagnosis, 2013, pp. 60–69.
Available: <http://www.halcyon.com/pub/journals/2Ips03-vidmar>
- [7] J. Pyrhönen, T. Jokinen, V. Hrabovcová, "Design of Rotating Electrical Machines", Wiley 2014
- [8] Y.CH.Chong, D. Staton, I. Egana, I.R. Argandona, A. Egea, "Thermal desing of a magnet-free axial-flux switch reluctance motor for automotive applications," 2016 Eleventh International Conference on Ecological Vehicles and Renewable Energies
- [9] A. Boglietti, D. Cavagnino, M.Staton, M. Mueller, and C. Mejuto, "Evolution and modern approaches for thermal analysis of electrical machines," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 871-882, Mar. 2009.
- [10] A. Boglietti, A. Cavagino, M. Lazzari, and M. Pastorelli, "A simplified thermal model for variable-speed self-cooled industrial induction motor," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 945-952, Jul/Aug. 2003.
- [11] B. Andreson, "Lumped Parameter Thermal Modeling of Electrical Machines, Analysis of an Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor for Vehicle Applications"
- [12] A. Kacemka, A.-C. Pop, I. Vintiloiu, D. Fodorean, Lumped Parameter Thermal Modeling of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor, Electric Vehicle International Conference & Show (EV2019), Bucharest, 3-4 October 2019, DOI 10.1109/EV.2019.8892937.
- [13] P. S. Ghahfarokhi, A. Kallaste, A. Belahcen, T. Vaimann, "Steady State and Transient Thermal Analysis of the Stator Coil of a Permanent Magnet Generator".
- [14] K. Witovski, M. Feucht, N. Stander, "An Effective Curve Matching Metric for Parameter Identification using Partial Mapping," 8th European LS-DYNA Users Conference, Strasbourg
- [15] C. Sciascera, P. Giagmde, L. Papini, Ch. Gerada, M. Galea, "Analytical Thermal Model for Fast Stator Winding Temperature Prediction," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronic*, VOL. 64, NO. 8, August 2017
- [16] N. Stander, W. Roux, A. Basudhar, T. Eggleston, T. Goel, K. Craig, "LS-OPT User's Manual A Design Optimization and Probabilistic Analysis Tool for the Engineering Analyst", December 2015

XI. BIOGRAPHIES

Andrej Kačenka was born in Ilava, Slovakia in 1994. He received his B.Sc and M.Sc. degree in electrical engineering and in electric drives, both from the Faculty of Electrical Engineering at the University of Zilina, Slovak Republic in 2016 and 2018 respectively. He is currently a Fellow of the Marie Curie Project INTERACT at the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania. Within this project, he worked as an electrical engineer at company Brose Fahrzeugteile SE & Co. KG, Würzburg in Germany. His professional and research interests cover design, optimization and control of electric machines and drives. He is the first author of 3 scientific papers.

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Adrian-C. Pop was born in Baia Mare, Romania in 1985. He received the M. Sc. Degree from the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, in 2010 in electrical engineering, and the Ph.D. degree in the framework of a joint-program between the Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, and the Université Libre de Bruxelles, Brussels, Belgium, in 2012. Since then he is with Brose Fahrzeugteile SE & Co. KG, Würzburg, Germany, within the Drives/Simulation Group. His current research is focused on optimal design for cost and performance of brushless AC and DC machines for automotive applications (i.e., light traction, power-train, chassis, and thermal management) by means of multiphysics analysis starting from the customer-provided requirements and specifications. His past and current subjects of interest include design and optimization of electrical machines and drives (SRMs, PMSMs, and IMs), numerical methods, and hybrid and electrical vehicles. Dr. Adrian-C. Pop is first author and co-author of some 25 scientific papers and 5 patents. He is member of the IEEE-IES electric machines technical committee.

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